

STATUS OF AMERICAN ENGLISH AS THE MULTINATIONAL LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This academic article discusses the causes and stages of development of the American English language. The purpose of the scientific work is to review and analyze the reasons why American English has the status of a multinational language.*

Key words: *independent language, multinational status, multi-ethnic states, inter-state and inter-ethnic relations, immigrants, global language, nationality, communication.*

СТАТУС АМЕРИКАНСКОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО КАК МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЯЗЫК.

Аннотация. *В этой академической статье рассматриваются причины и этапы развития американского английского языка. Цель научной работы – рассмотреть и проанализировать причины, по которым американский английский имеет статус многонационального языка.*

Ключевые слова: *независимый язык, многонациональный статус, полиэтнические государства, межгосударственные и межэтнические отношения, иммигранты, глобальный язык, национальность, общение.*

Today, English is the most common language, but not the only one, spoken in the United States. Let's assume that American English is an independent language. Then it must have its own historically established system of sound, vocabulary and grammatical means, which objectifies the work of thinking and is a tool for communication, exchange of thoughts and mutual understanding of people in society (in accordance with the definition). Therefore, it is necessary to find out its origin more precisely, how it appeared in America, as well as how the system of sound, vocabulary and grammatical means historically developed.

Having turned to historical and geographical reference books for information, I found out the following information. At the beginning of the seventeenth century, colonists from England began to bring their language to America. In 1607, John Smith founded the first colony in Virginia. And already at the beginning of the 17th century, Europeans began to move to North America.¹

At the beginning there were only a small number of settlers, but after three centuries there were millions of them. People left in the hope of a new, rich, free life full of interesting events and adventures. He created a completely new society with its own laws, life principles, its own economic structure, and its own statehood. People left for America for various reasons: some hoped to get rich quickly, some were hiding from persecution by the punishing hand of the law, some wanted to gain political freedom, and some wanted to get rid of religious persecution and gain freedom of religion. There were many reasons. People came to America from different European countries. But most of the colonists came from England. Therefore, it was English that became the main language of communication in the then still emerging huge country. At the initial

¹ <https://infourok.ru/statya-istoriya-vozniknoveniya-amerikanskogo-angliyskogo-yazika-3878027.html>

stage, American English was not much different from British. English colonists came from different regions of Great Britain, and the language of groups of people from different regions differed both in the pronunciation of individual words and in the use of lexical phrases. There was no uniformity or norms in the written language. Years passed, centuries passed, and emigrants who arrived later made their own changes to the vocabulary, phonetics and grammar of the language - throughout the 18th-20th centuries, their native language changed. Other linguistic groups of people who came to live and work in America from European countries also made their contribution to the formation of the language. These were Spaniards and Italians, Scandinavians and Germans, French and Russians.

During the development of American English, the basic principle was laid down - simplification of the language. Ordinary, simple people, leaving their entire past behind, went to America in the hope of finding happiness. And they needed a simple and accessible way of communication that would unite all nationalities. Today, the English spoken by Americans is not as diverse as it was during the founding of the United States of America. American English is clearly regulated and is the main language of communication and has the status of the state language.

In the era of globalization, due to the self-determination of the peoples of the world, the formation of multi-ethnic states, inter-state and inter-ethnic relations, and the processes of active population migration, the legal solution of language issues has become one of the main tasks of the state. These issues relate to the topic of legislative support for the use of languages in formal and informal communication, in language teaching at school and university, and in people-to-people relations.² In the US, there is a constant struggle between the two sides of political correctness: official Americanism and official multiculturalism. There are not so many differences between them as it seems at first glance. After all, only superficial ethnographic features of non-American cultures have survived. Modern integration processes do not reduce the level of social stratification of society, and only the forms of the language change. Alternatively, social stratification is becoming a more universal and important feature of English in the United States than regional differentiation.³ In this case, describing the linguistic situation in the United States is interpreted as more work than less.⁴ In order to shed light on the language situation in the United States, it is necessary to reveal the nature and general characteristics of the language situation, in which the current situation in the United States, the languages spoken in this country and the immigrants who contribute to the development of the English language and the impact of their different cultures are significant⁵.

Sociolinguistics is used to study the role and position of language in a particular society.

² Гречко, В. А. Теория языкознания: Учеб. пособие/В. А. Гречко.— М.: Высш шк., 2003.— с.315

³ Швейцер А. Д., Социальная дифференциация английского языка в США, М., 1983. — с.37,38,54,78

⁴ Нигматуллина, Л. М. Языковая ситуация в США / Л. М. Нигматуллина, А. А. Скуратова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2014. — № 21 (80). — С. 785-789. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/80/14380/> (дата обращения: 28.04.2024).

⁵ Ощепкова В. В. Язык и культура Великобритании, США, Канады, Австралии, Новой Зеландии. — М./СПб.: ГПОССА/КАРО, 2004. — с.45,46,53

One of the main concepts of sociolinguistics is the concept of linguistic situation. The place of language in society is analyzed through case studies.⁶ "The concept of language situation is usually applied to large language communities - countries, regions, republics. The time factor is important for this concept: in essence, the language situation is a characteristic of the socio-communicative system in a certain period of activity."⁷ In the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary edited by V. N. Yartseva, the following definition is given to this concept: "forms of existence of a language, as well as styles or a set of their regional-social languages. Certain geographical regions or administrative- Relations and functional interaction of political objects are the main subject of sociolinguistics. Linguistic situation is a set of languages and variants of languages that serve a given society ethnically and multi-ethnically: dialects, slangs, functional styles and other forms of language existence; a specific territory, political territorial unit or state borders."⁸ The most general definition was given by V. N. Avorin, and this term is "a specific type of interaction of languages and at a certain stage of their historical development in the social life of each nation different forms of existence". .. It is a component of the most complex structure of social relations within this or that group of people." It should also be noted that there is a narrower understanding of language state, which is related to the concept of language state as a set of state components: functional methods, forms of existence and forms of implementation.

When talking about the English language, it is divided into categories with the names American dialect or British English, but what is the status of English in America, and what is the official language? There is no single official language for everyone in the United States. English is only the dominant language⁹ in the states because it is spoken by a large part of the population. The issue of language has been and continues to be controversial in the United States. However, 27 states have adopted English as an official language. A great example is the state of Hawaii, where English and Hawaiian are the official languages¹⁰. New Mexico has a law that provides for the use of English and Spanish, and Louisiana for English and French, but neither language is declared official. Island territories with associated status (essentially United States overseas possessions) provide official recognition of local languages alongside English: Samoan and Chamorro are recognized in American Samoa and Guam, respectively; Caroline and Chamorro are recognized in the Northern Mariana Islands; Spanish is the official language of Puerto Rico.¹¹

If people look at the history of the United States of America, over the years and centuries, the population of this country has been constantly filled with immigrants: at first, mainly from Western and Central European countries - Germany, Ireland, England, etc., and by the end of the 19th century, southern and immigrants from south-eastern Europe - Italy, Austria-Hungary, Tsarist Russia. As they integrated into American society, all of these groups were influenced by the

⁶ Мечковская Н. Б. Социальная лингвистика: Пособие для студентов гуманитарных вузов и учащихся лицеев. — М.: Аспект Пресс, 2000. — с.101–102 8.

⁷ Беликов В. И., Крысин Л. П. Социоллингвистика. — М.: РГГУ, 2001. — с.26–27

⁸ Беликов В. И., Крысин Л. П. Социоллингвистика. — М.: РГГУ, 2001. — с.26–27

⁹ Гречко, В. А. Теория языкознания: Учеб. пособие/В. А. Гречко.— М.: Высш шк., 2003.— с.315 5.

¹⁰ Crystal D. English as a global language / D. Crystal; lane from English N.V. Kuznetsova. - М.: Ves Mir, 2001. - p.60

¹¹ Нигматуллина, Л. М. Языковая ситуация в США / Л. М. Нигматуллина, А. А. Скуратова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2014. — № 21 (80). — С. 785-789. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/80/14380/> (дата обращения: 28.04.2024).

general American environment. In the process of their adaptation, mastering the values of the dominant culture, which had already been formed, mastering the English language played an important role as the most important element of the acculturation process. Now, Spanish-speaking immigrants, particularly in the American Southwest, are expressing their desire to use their own language, and many Americans see it as a threat that could divide the country. Currently, in some areas of the country, especially in the southwest, up to 90% of the population is Hispanic. All information here is in English and Spanish. This situation led to the formation of a social movement called the 'One English Movement', which aims to make English the official language of the United States. It should also be noted that throughout the country's history, school remains the most effective method of Americanization and loss of native languages. There are almost no schools for people of different nationalities in the language spoken by their own country. The language of instruction in all public and private schools at all levels is English only. Regarding the state of the common language, the US English Language Foundation published the report "Many Languages - One America" in March 2005. As noted in this work, the most common native language in the United States is English, with 215.4 million of the 293 million Americans (73.5%) speaking it as their first language. Spanish is the native language of 28 million US residents (10.7%). This is evidenced by the fact that bilingualism in the United States is widespread, mainly among non-English speakers, first and to some extent second generation immigrants, forced to adapt to the dominant way of life. Culture and language adapted.¹² The further development of the language situation in the United States will depend on:

- maintaining and strengthening the status of the only powerful country, which is to some extent responsible for the unprecedented role of the English language in the modern world;
- continuation of mass emigration;
- The ideological evolution of the United States in the direction of more multiculturalism or, conversely, more rigid cultural homogeneity.

The situation in America and its paradox is that in the country, especially in the megacities of both coasts, the amazing diversity of literally all the languages of the world is provided by different languages, but in proportion to the common intercultural language. A steady stream of new immigrants and, on the other hand, most people entering the country are under the age of 15, and most of them are second-generation Americans. The synthesis of all these factors creates the unique content of a country that does not have a state language in the Constitution, but there are many languages that are widely spoken throughout America. Each state has one or two languages, one of which may be the mother tongue of the indigenous people living in that area. In general, based on the above, it should be noted that it is the English language that is still the most common native language in the United States of America, which allowed to preserve the unity of the American people in the era of cultural diversity throughout the world. There have been attempts to formalize English, but they have failed due to fears of discrimination against immigrants.

Originally, the territory of the present United States of America was inhabited by Indians who spoke more than 300 languages and dialects. With the arrival of European colonists, English, French, German and other languages appeared. By the time the United States was founded in 1776,

¹² Schweitzer A.D., Social differentiation of the English language in the USA, M., 1983. - pp. 37,38,54,78

most of the people in the colonies spoke English. However, the founders of the country did not declare English as the official language in order not to offend those whose mother tongue is another language.¹³

However, America accepts immigrants from many countries for citizenship, and if they have any talent or skill in the field of work, it creates many opportunities for them. As everyone knows, America has opened its doors to all nations in terms of education, every year it announces millions of grants for education, and on the basis of this announcement, accepts students for education, study there are many jobs after graduation. Many nationalities go to America for work in different countries; the goal is to earn more. Such emigrations have been going on for years, and many nationalities and peoples are now living in America. Despite the fact that they belong to different nationalities and cultures, the main element of their communication is the English language. And this is the only reason why the English language has the status of a multinational in the United States of America.

As immigration to the United States has increased, so has linguistic diversity. For example, Spanish became widespread after the annexation of Mexico. But English has always been dominant. Today, the situation is different in different states. English is still the official language in 32 states. Some states recognize indigenous languages along with it, such as Hawaiian or Alaskan Indian languages. Despite the lack of official status, English is spoken by the majority of the population. It is common in all aspects of American society, making it practically the national language. In general, today, along with the status of the English language as a global language, English has become a multinational status in America.

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